

A Drone-Assisted 3D Printing by Crane Structures in Construction Industry

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Abstract—In this paper a different paradigm to exploit the additive manufacturing in the construction industry is given starting from well studied and settled technologies like tower crane and drones. A preliminary model is studied, its feasibility is investigated and the promising results of this first study are presented. Finally, the baseline and path for future investigation for the real development of this approach are enlightened.

I. INTRODUCTION

Construction industry is historically characterized by delay in the adoption of new technologies and innovative production processes [2][1].

Among robotic technologies applied to constructions, an important role is played by additive manufacturing. The limitations in the application of such a technology in construction industry drive researchers to develop new fabrication strategies [3].

The main question that is attempted to be answered in this paper is: why should new technologies be researched for if the integration of existing ones could foster the application of the additive manufacturing to a real construction scale? The mean idea investigated in this paper is that the integration of the well settled tower crane technology with the strong modern UAV technologies can contribute significantly to the involvement of additive manufacturing in construction industry.

Without tower cranes, modern buildings and constructions dimensions would be impossible to reach. Since they are so important and technologically developed, an idea is to try to use them as a support for large scale additive manufacturing.

In this paper, an extruder suspended to the crane can deposit viscous material layer by layer. The swing effect that can compromise the results of such operation is corrected with a direct control on the extruder performed by a drone, that has only to direct and lead the suspended load and not to carry and precisely locate any heavy load.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

A. Problem Description

An overhead crane structure is studied considering a simple dynamical model.

In the present study, the suspended mass is represented by an extruder for viscous materials (such as concrete or clay). This extruder has to follow a predetermined trajectory that

Fig. 1. Considered model.

describes the object to 3d print; the extruder deposits material over other material to create the object layer by layer. The extruder swing behavior is controlled by a drone that can sense the load state and can act to compensate the swing. In particular, a semi-circular wall is chosen as a trajectory with radius $r = 2m$ (Fig. 1); it is followed by the trolley that is the only actuated element of the system. Consequently to the trolley actuation, the suspended extruder is subjected only to inertial forces depending on its mass. The drone has to sense its deviation from the desired vertical position and act to reduce the swing.

B. Equations of motion and Linear System Model

The overhead crane is modeled as a pendulum free to swing in both directions and the dynamical model is obtained by using Lagrange modeling method:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{q}}} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right) = \mathbf{F}(t) \quad (1)$$

where L is the Lagrangian function, $\mathbf{q} = [\theta, x, \phi, y]^T$ is the vector of physical degrees of freedom. In particular, θ and ϕ are the angles that the extruder creates with the vertical when subjected to swing respectively in along x and y axes, $x(t)$ and $y(t)$ are the movements in x and y axes directions of the trolley (see Fig. 1). Moreover, $\mathbf{F} = [-b\dot{\theta}, F_x, -b\dot{\phi}, F_y]^T$ is the vector of forces: F_x and F_y are the forces acting in x and y axes directions of the trolley, b is the viscous rotational friction of the extruder during the swing (Fig. 1).

The obtained model is a non linear, time-dependent and four order system. With basic assumptions and by performing the calculations, the system is expressed in the form of a linearized State-Space system:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u} \quad (2)$$

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Fig. 2. Non-controlled trajectory (a) and controlled trajectory (b)

where

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{g}{l(i)} & \frac{b}{l^2 m} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{g}{l(i)} & \frac{b}{l^2 m} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{y} \\ d_1 \\ d_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1/l(i) & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/l(i) & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Since the system is controllable, the inputs of the system are controlled by the drone by the following static state feedback:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{r}(t) - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{x}(t) \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the state feedback matrix, and the $\mathbf{r}(t) = [\ddot{x}, \ddot{y}, 0, 0]^T$ is the reference input.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In Fig. 2 a graphical results of the simulated system both in non-controlled and controlled situation is shown.

Fig. 3 shows the first layer of material deposition and a visual comparison between the desired trajectory that is the one followed by the trolley (in black, the desired trajectory), the controlled trajectory (in blue) and the non-controlled trajectory of the free extruder (in red), absolutely unsuitable.

Fig. 4 shows numerically how much worst the non-controlled approach is in comparison with the controlled one. The red curve represents the mean squared error of the red trajectory of Fig. 3, that reaches about $mse = 0.30m$ in the worst case. The blue curve instead represent the mean squared error of the blue trajectory of Fig. 3.

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Fig. 3. Trajectories on the first layer

Fig. 4. Mean squared error of the non-controlled system and of the controlled system

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